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ABSTRACT

The present study is dedicated to the competitiveness of health tourism in Bulgaria in the context of the dynamically developing global and European market for health-tourism services. The research aims to identify its main competitors and to formulate guidelines for the development of the sector.

The methodological approach includes analysis of specialized literature, regulatory documents and market data, as well as a survey conducted in the period February–April 2026 among 453 respondents.

The results show that Bulgaria has significant potential for the development of health tourism, based on a rich resource of mineral waters, favorable natural conditions, traditions in balneotherapy, and opportunities to combine medical, rehabilitation and tourism services. However, the country lags behind its main competitors in terms of international recognition, marketing, infrastructure, accreditation, digitalization and institutional coordination.

It has been established that the main users of health tourism in Bulgaria are citizens of European countries, mostly from Germany, Greece and Romania, while Turkey stands out as the leading regional competitor. The analysis identifies key barriers to the development of the sector: insufficient funding, weak international visibility, poor transport connectivity, a limited number of international certifications, seasonality, digital underdevelopment and insufficient coordination between the sectors of healthcare, tourism and public administration.

Keywords: Health tourism, medical tourism, balneotourism, SPA and wellness, competition and market of health tourism services.

INTRODUCTION

Health tourism is among the most dynamically developing segments of tourism because it combines prevention, treatment, rehabilitation and wellness into an integrated consumer experience. Bulgaria has mineral springs, a favorable climate, traditions in balneotherapy and the opportunity to combine medical services with natural and tourism resources. The country ranks first in Europe in terms of number and diversity of mineral springs, with 102 resorts and over 600 mineral water sources, yet it significantly lags behind regional competitors in marketing, infrastructure and institutional organization. The development of the sector has the potential to enhance the country's competitiveness, attract international visitors and stimulate the regional economy and employment. Alongside this potential, problems emerge in organization, management, financing, coordination and international popularity, which necessitate an in-depth study and practical recommendations. Health tourism in Bulgaria is at a crossroads between huge untapped potential and acute competitive challenges. The global medical tourism market was valued at USD 47–55 billion in 2024 and is expected to reach USD 221 billion by 2033 with a CAGR of 18.8%, representing a strategic window for Bulgaria's positioning.

AIM, OBJECTIVES AND METHODS

The aim of this study is, on the basis of an in-depth analysis of available literature and a proprietary survey,

to assess the position of Bulgaria on the European market of health tourism services, to determine its main competitors and to formulate recommendations for development.

To achieve this aim, we set the following main objectives:

1. To analyze the state and position of Bulgaria on the market of health tourism services.
2. To identify the main competitors, their advantages and disadvantages.
3. Based on the analysis, to formulate recommendations for the development of health tourism in Bulgaria.

ANALYSIS

In the period February–April 2026 a survey was conducted covering 453 respondents – users of health tourism (41.94%), representatives of healthcare facilities (26.93%), local/national administration and students at medical universities and medical colleges. The largest share of respondents are from the capital (41.06%), followed by residents of towns (36.20%) and villages and regional centers. Part of the questions in the survey address the position of Bulgaria on the market of health tourism services, the competitive environment and the main tourism flows.

Fig. 1. From which countries do most users of health tourism in Bulgaria come?

As can be seen from Fig. 1, the respondents indicate that the main users of health tourism in Bulgaria (72.41%) are citizens of European countries, primarily from Germany, Greece and Romania. This is entirely understandable – German citizens are traditional tourists for Bulgaria who have been familiar with and have benefited from Bulgaria’s natural and tourism opportunities over the last 60–70 years. Greece and Romania are neighboring countries and the opportunities that Bulgaria offers are well known to them, while their location allows for frequent visits not only for longer stays, but even for short-term weekend trips. In second place (18.98%) are citizens from Russia and the CIS, who constitute a significant but geopolitically risky market. Users of health tourism services from the Middle East are few (3.75%), which is a prerequisite for the development of this small but high-potential market.

Turkey is the main competitor, identified by 19.23% of respondents. It emerges as the dominant regional competitor. The Turkish medical tourism market was valued at USD 1.89 billion for 2023 and is expected to reach USD 3.48 billion by 2029 with a CAGR of 10.51%. As of 2026, its market value is already estimated at USD 4.60 billion, with a forecast of USD 12.01 billion by 2033.

Turkey attracts patients with medical costs 70–90% lower than those in Western Europe, North Amer-

ica and the United Kingdom. The country has numerous JCI-accredited hospitals and clinics and active government support with investments of USD 50 billion in public healthcare for 2024. Turkey handles over 1.2 million international dental patients per year – about four times more than Hungary, and the country itself reported 701,046 health tourists only for 2019.

According to the respondents, the main competitors from the EU are Germany (6.59%), Italy (6.04%), Austria (4.40%), Romania (4.40%) and the Czech Republic (3.30%), which is formed on the basis of personal observation/experience and professional knowledge of the surveyed individuals. This largely overlaps with other studies of ours, according to which the main competitors from the EU are countries such as Hungary, the Czech Republic, Austria and Slovenia. Hungary has built an international brand “Land of Spas” and “City of Baths” (Budapest), with a focus on balneotherapy, wellness hotels, historic baths and dental clinics. German patients have remained a dominant market for Hungary for decades, and the country positions itself within the EU regulatory framework – a significant advantage over Turkey. The Czech Republic, Austria and Slovenia are identified as direct competitors of Hungary in balneotherapy and SPA tourism. EU health tourism accounts for around 5% of total tourism in the EU and contributes approximately 0.3% to the European economy.

Fig. 2. Main obstacles to the development of health tourism in Bulgaria

Figure 2 presents the answers to the question “In your opinion, what are the main obstacles to the development of health tourism in Bulgaria?” The question is multiple-choice – respondents can give more than one answer and therefore the total number of responses exceeds 100%.

We can present the main problems and challenges in three aspects – structural, market-related and institutional.

Structural challenges

Insufficient international visibility and marketing is Bulgaria’s critical weakness. A significant share (44.37%) of respondents point to low international popularity as an obstacle to the development of health tourism in the country. In Turkey we observe the exact opposite. There, the state invests aggressively in marketing and advertising for tourism development with the participation of government agencies and global partnerships.

Weak transport connectivity around balneo-destinations is directly identified by the chair of BUBSPA, Siika Katsarova, as a major problem. The EBRD strategy for Bulgaria 2025–2030 confirms that road infrastructure is still insufficient and the railway network requires substantial upgrades.

Respondents point to insufficient funding (68.65%) as a major obstacle to development. At the same time, Turkey alone allocated USD 50 billion for healthcare in 2024, with this large investment aimed at stimulating the development of modern medical infrastructure that will attract international patients and develop the country’s medical tourism market.

Limited JCI accreditation and international certifications reduces foreign patients’ trust. The shortage of medical and rehabilitation professionals is directly mentioned by BUBSPA as a significant problem, although the country is among the leading in the EU in number of physicians and dentists per 100,000 inhabitants.

Market challenges

Seasonality – despite the potential for year-round tourism, actual utilization remains uneven. Scientific literature confirms that increasing the share of health tourism can reduce seasonality. Hungary has succeeded

in reducing seasonal fluctuations through investments in SPA destinations.

Digital underdevelopment in marketing and online presence. A study of digital tourism platforms in Bulgaria identifies “weak digital presence in smaller municipalities” and “poor integration with social networks”.

Price competition with Turkey: Turkey offers dental implants at EUR 400–800 compared to EUR 600–1,000 in Hungary, but price is only one of the factors. In choosing a destination for health tourism, costs of transport (flights), hotels and living expenses are important, as well as the possibility of combining treatment with leisure and language support (for example, in Turkey Smile & Holiday offers coordination in six languages). Bulgaria competes primarily on price, but Turkey offers lower prices with more modern infrastructure.

The exclusion of private medical SPA centers from contracts with the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) and the lack of funding from the National Social Security Institute places the private sector at a disadvantage compared to subsidized competitors.

Institutional challenges

Lack of coordination between healthcare, tourism and public administration – 59.60% of respondents indicate it as a major barrier. Turkey’s successful model includes a single government agency coordinating all aspects of medical tourism.

Regulatory framework – despite the existence of Ordinance No. 04-14 of 2019 for the certification of balneotherapy centers, changes in the regulatory framework lag behind market dynamics.

On the basis of the analysis we can formulate the following **main directions** aimed at increasing competitiveness and developing health tourism in Bulgaria.

Differentiation from Turkey

Bulgaria should not compete head-on with Turkey on price, but should build a different market position based on:

- EU security and regulatory framework – for Western European patients, especially German and Austrian, EU membership and GDPR are decisive advantages.

- Natural authenticity and balneotherapy – positioning as a “green, authentic alternative” with an emphasis on mineral springs and nature, unlike Turkey, which is oriented towards medical procedures.
- Integrated wellness packages – combining medical procedures with ecotourism, mountain nature and rich historical heritage.
- Year-round destination – unlike Turkey with a focus on seaside and urban tourism, Bulgaria can offer a ski-SPA winter product (Bansko), a mountain summer product and marine rehabilitation.

Competitive strategies against EU destinations (Hungary, Czech Republic, Austria, etc.)

Bulgaria should:

- Brand its balneo-destinations by analogy with Budapest (“City of Baths”) and Karlovy Vary – developing the concept “Velinograd – the SPA capital of the Balkans”.
- Invest in accreditation – large-scale introduction of JCI, ISO and European medical certifications to increase trust.
- Attract German and Austrian markets – there are already successful contracts with German health funds, which are a ready channel for scaling.
- Integrate wellness innovations – digital detox, yoga retreats, meditation and sports tourism with traditional balneotherapy services.

Institutional reforms

- A unified coordination structure following Turkey’s model – a government agency combining health, tourism and investment competencies.
- Inclusion of private medical SPA centers in NHIF and NSSI schemes to reduce the financial burden and increase accessibility.
- Simplification of licensing and certification for health-tourism facilities.
- Strategic partnerships with Destination Management Organizations (DMOs), following models successfully applied in other tourism regions.

Marketing and digitalization

- Participation in 27 international tourism fairs – the plans of the Ministry of Tourism for 2025 include presence on key markets, which should be specified with health-tourism content.
- Partnerships with global platforms – National Geographic, BBC, CNN, Google, Meta and [Booking.com](https://www.booking.com) for targeted health-tourism campaigns.
- A unified digital platform for health tourism with a multilingual interface, facility accreditations and online booking.
- Influencer marketing with a focus on wellness and balneotourism to reach younger audiences (the 31–50 age group is dominant).

Infrastructure investments

- Transport connectivity to balneo-destinations – construction or rehabilitation of roads to Velinograd, Sapareva Banya, Narechenski Bani.
- Modernization of the hotel base – only 3.97% of respondents rate the material base as excellent, which requires attracting foreign investment through incentives and European funds.

- Specialized medical centers for targeted development of medical tourism – eye surgery, dental services, orthopedics and rehabilitation.

Using a new competitive advantage – Schengen and the euro

- Schengen membership eliminates border controls and is already showing a tangible increase in short-term car tourism from neighboring countries.
- The Eurozone (from 1 January 2026) allows tourists to compare prices directly and eliminates currency risk – a key advantage for German and Austrian patients.

CONCLUSION

From the analysis conducted we can conclude that Bulgaria possesses unique competitive advantages – especially in balneology and natural resources – but needs systemic reforms to transform this potential into competitiveness. Health tourism in Bulgaria has real potential to become a strategically important sector with high added value for the national economy, regional development and the international image of the country. The analysis shows that Bulgaria has objective advantages related to natural resources, traditions in balneotherapy and the opportunities to combine treatment, rehabilitation, prevention and tourism experience, but still fails to turn them into a sustainable competitive advantage.

The main reasons for this are related not so much to lack of resources as to insufficient strategic organization, limited international recognition, infrastructure deficits, insufficient digitalization and the absence of a coordinated state policy. In the context of strong competition from Turkey and established European destinations, the future development of health tourism in Bulgaria should be based on clear market positioning, institutional integration, investments in quality and branding, as well as on the creation of innovative and year-round health-tourism products.

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